

A Convergent Synthesis of Taxamairin A, B Precursor I. 8-(2,3-Dimethoxy-4-isopropylbenzyl)-1,4-dioxaspiro[4,5]decan-7-one

XUECHAO WANG and XINFU PAN*

Department of Chemistry, National Laboratory of Applied Organic Chemistry, Lanzhou University, Lanzhou 730000, China

Manuscript received 17 November 1994, accepted 12 January 1995

The rearranged 9(10 → 20)-abeo-abietane skeleton, a rare structural type of diterpene thought to arise from the rearrangement of the more familiar abietane skeleton¹ has received considerable attention in the last few years. Several new members of this group have been isolated², and their total or partial syntheses have been reported³. Among of them, taxamairin A(1), B(2), have been recently isolated⁴ from the bark of *Taxus mairei* Lemee et Levl. S. Y. As a part of our synthetic studies on the naturally occurring diterpenes, we have attempted to synthesise them. The synthetic strategy was developed from a retrosynthetic analysis of the natural product 2 (Scheme 1). Herein we report the synthesis of the key intermediate 4.

The route to the key intermediate 4 is shown in Scheme 2. 1,2-Dimethoxy-3-isopropylbenzene (9), readily available from 2,3-dimethoxybenzaldehyde in 42% overall yield⁵, was lithiated with butyllithium, followed by addition of paraformaldehyde to give 2,3-dimethoxy-4-isopropylbenzyl alcohol (10). Compound 10 was brominated with phosphorus tribromide to afford 2,3-dimethoxy-4-isopropylbenzyl bromide (5).

The requisite fragment (6) was readily derived from 1,3-cyclohexandione (8). In the presence of potassium carbonate, 8 was reacted with iodomethane to form 2,2-methyl-1,3-cyclohexandione (11) through an one-pot reaction. The desired fragment (6) was easily obtained by the condensation of 11 with ethylene glycol at the catalysis of $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$.

The coupling reaction of 6 and 5 was conducted conveniently in the presence of potassium hydride to yield the product (4). The routes of Wittig, Knoevenagel and Reformatsky reactions for the synthesis of 3 from 4 failed,

Scheme 2 Reagents (a) Ref 5, (b) 1, BuLi, THF, 2, $(\text{CH}_2\text{O})_n$, (c) PBr_3 , CH_2Cl_2 , (d) CH_3I , K_2CO_3 , (e) ethylene glycol, $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$, (f) KH, THF, then followed by addition of 5

the steric hindrance being accounted for them, The further studies on converting 4 to taxamairin A, B are in progress.

Experimental

IR spectra were recorded on a FT-170SX spectrophotometer, nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a FT-80A or a Bruker AM-400 spectrometer with TMS as the internal standard and mass spectra on a ZAB-HS spectrometer. All compounds were purified by distillation under vacuum or flash chromatography (FCG) on silica gel-H (10–40 μm) (Qing Dao Mairine Chemical) eluting with the solvent mixture of petroleum ether and ethyl acetate.

2,3-Dimethoxy-4-isopropylbenzyl alcohol (10) : To a solution of 9 (5.4 g, 0.03 mol) and TMEDA (6.23 ml, 0.0416 mol) in absolute ether (38 ml) was added a solution of butyllithium (1.6 M; 25 ml) in ether under N_2 . The mixture was cooled to 0–5° and paraformaldehyde (1.3 g, 0.0433 mol) was portionwise added with vigorous stirring. The mixture was stirred overnight, 5% HCl (50 ml) was added slowly and the resulting solution was extracted with ether (4 × 250 ml). The ether-extract was washed with 5% HCl (25 ml), saturated NaHCO_3 (40 ml), brine (2 × 50 ml), dried over sodium sulphate and evaporated. The residue

was purified by FCG to give **10** (5.9 g, 94%); m/z 210 (100), 195 (58), 177 (88), 165 (51); δ 6.96 (1H, d, J 7.9 Hz), 6.89 (1H, d, J 7.9 Hz), 4.62 (2H, s), 3.87 (3H, s), 3.84 (3H, s), 3.24 (1H, sept. J 6.9 Hz), 2.22 (1H, s), 1.19 (6H, d, J 6.9 Hz); ν_{\max} 3 383, 2 966, 2 834, 1 272, 1 173, 1 086 cm^{-1} .

2,3-Dimethoxy-4-isopropylbenzyl bromide (5) : To a solution of **10** (4.2 g, 0.02 mol) in anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 (30 ml), was added dropwise PBr_3 (5.32 g, 0.02 mol) at room temperature. The mixture was stirred for 15 min and then wet NaHCO_3 was added until pH 8–9. The crude product was purified by FCG to give **5** (5.32 g, 97%) as colourless oil; m/z 276 (9), 274 (10), 193 (100) 178 (30), 105 (19); δ 7.08 (1H, d, J 8.1 Hz), 6.92 (1H, d, J 8.1 Hz), 4.54 (2H, s), 3.97 (3H, s), 3.84 (3H, s), 3.31 (1H, sept. J 6.9 Hz), 1.21 (6H, d, J 6.9 Hz); ν_{\max} 2 967, 2 840, 1 229, 1 054, 590, 555 cm^{-1} .

2,2-Dimethylcyclohexanone (11) : To a solution of **8** (22.4 g, 0.20 mol) and acetone (240 ml), were added anhydrous K_2CO_3 (57.4 g, 0.42 mol) and iodomethane (71 g, 0.50 mol). The mixture was stirred for 13 h and then cooled to room temperature followed by addition of chloroform (240 ml). The residue was distilled under vacuum to give **11** (15.1 g, 54%), b.p. 84–85°/4 mm Hg; m/z 140 (59), 125 (28), 97 (100); δ 2.69 (4H, t, J 6.8 Hz), 1.98 (2H, p, J 6.8 Hz), 1.31 (6H, s); ν_{\max} 2 988, 2 952, 2 857, 1 780, 1 384, 1 131, 1 082 cm^{-1} .

1,4-Dioxaspiro[4,5]decan-7-one (6) : To a solution of **11** (5 g, 0.043 mol) and ethylene glycol (2.8 g, 0.045 mol) in absolute ether (60 ml), was added catalytic amount of $\text{BF}_3\text{Et}_2\text{O}$ (0.047 mol). The mixture was stirred for 2 h and then the ether was evaporated. The residue was purified by FCG to give **6** (5.59 g, 85%); m/z 184 (100), 141 (39), 99 (65); δ 3.79 (4H, s), 2.51 (2H, m), 2.46 (2H, m), 1.85 (2H, m), 1.81 (6H, s); ν_{\max} 2 988, 2 952, 2 857, 1 780, 1 384, 1 131, 1 082 cm^{-1} .

6-(2,3-Dimethoxy-4-isopropylbenzyl)-1,4-dioxaspiro[4,5]decan-7-one (4) : To a solution of **KH** (0.53 g, 0.014 mol) in THF (15 ml), was added **6** (1.84 g, 0.01 mol) in THF (10 ml). The resulting solution of **5** (3.01 g, 0.011 mol) in THF (10 ml) was added dropwise. The solution was stirred for another 24 h at room temperature and water (8 ml) was added to quench the reaction. The mixture was then extracted with ether (4×30 ml), the ether-extract washed with brine (2×10 ml) and evaporated. The residue was purified by FCG to give **4** (3.23 g, 86%); m/z 376 (62), 361 (48), 345 (27), 140 (100); δ 6.71 (1H, d, J 8.1 Hz), 6.69 (1H, d, J 8.1 Hz), 3.89, 3.87 (6H, ss), 3.81 (4H, s), 3.74, 3.59 (2H, d, J 11.3 Hz), 2.93 (1H, sept., J 7.4 Hz), 2.71 (1H, m), 2.42 (2H, m), 1.74 (2H, m), 1.25, 1.24 (6H, ss) 1.19 (6H, d, J 7.4 Hz); ν_{\max} 2 955, 2 970, 1 705, 1 083, 1 044 cm^{-1} .

References

- 1 A KELECOM, *Tetrahedron*, 1983, **39**, 3603.
- 2 A KELECOM and L B MEDEROS, *Bull Soc Chim Belg*, 1989, **98**, 413, Y ENDO, T OHTA, ENDO and S NOZOE, *Tetrahedron Lett*, 1991, **32**, 3083. S HASEGAWA, T KOJIMA and Y HIROSI, *Phytochemistry*, 1985, **24**, 1545, X A DOMINGUEZ, H SANCHEZ, V S GARICIA and G ESPINOSA, *J Natural Prod*, 1992, **55**, 221.
- 3 E R KOFT, *Tetrahedron*, 1987, **43**, 5775, T MATSUMOTO, S IMAI, T YOSHINARI and S MATSUNO, *Bull Chem Soc Jpn*, 1986, **59**, 3103, S DEB, G BHATTACHARJEE and U R GHATAK, *J Chem Soc, Perkin Trans 1*, 1990, 1453. A K GHOSH, C RAY and U R GHATAK, *Tetrahedron Lett*, 1992, **33**, 665, G MAJETICH, Y ZHANG, T L FELTMAN and J S DUNCAN *Tetrahedron Lett*, 1993, **34**, 445, X C WANG, Y X CUI and X F PAN, *Chin Chem Lett*, 1994, **5**, 475, X C WANG, Y X CUI, X F PAN and Y Z CHEN, *Indian J Chem*, (in Press).
- 4 J Y LIANG, Z D MIN, T TANAKA, M MIZUNO and M LLNUMA *Acta Chimica Sinica*, 1988, **46**, 21.
- 5 J D EDWARDS and J L CASHAW, *J Org Chem*, 1955 **26**, 847.
- 6 K Y GEETHA, K RAJAGOPALAN and S SWAMINATHAN, *Tetrahedron*, 1978, 2201.